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A marker of the B2 phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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We measured total transcription in fibroblasts from the terminal ileum of the small intestine in humans with B1, B2, or B3 phenotype Crohn's Disease to identify specific markers of the stenotic (fibrotic) or stricturing phenotype (B2). We report here identification of cell surface markers TMEM171 and TMEM256 as genes whose expression was indicative of the B2 phenotype. Fibroblasts from the terminal ileum of humans with B2 phenotype Crohn's Disease were IL-18+.